

Preliminary Approach to Calculate the Gamma Function without Numerical Integration

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Abstract:- We propose a semi-statistical technique to calculate the value of the Gamma function $G(x)$ in the whole space of positive x , i.e. $0 < x < \infty$.

The proposed method is rather simple and applies a second-degree polynomial fit to find accurate values for $G(x)$ in the interval $0 < x < 2$.

The precision of the numerical results of the new method is striking as presented in Table I where the absolute error is limited to less than 0.01 for the interval considered (x element of $]0.5]$).

We recommend the application of the proposed technique for practical purposes of calculating the gamma function in order to avoid the complication of its numerical integration.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Gamma function $G(x)$ is well defined for any positive value of x ,

$$G(x) = \int_0^{\infty} [e^{-z} z^x] dz \dots (1)$$

Needless to say, the special function Gamma as expressed by Equation 1 has great mathematical and physical significance.

Unfortunately, it is only for integer multiples of $1/2$, that the integral (1) and therefore the values of Gamma have an exact analytic expression.

Many researches have been recently published to numerically evaluate the Gamma integral (1) using approximate numerical integration methods such as Simpson and trapezoidal rules...etc [1,2,3]

However, for practical purposes, it can also be calculated using a suitable closed-form polynomial expression to avoid going through complicated numerical integration.

This is the subject of this article.

Below we propose a special statistical technique to find a polynomial fit in quadrature (just of order 2) to avoid the complications of higher order polynomials of n up to 10 for example.

The numerical results of the proposed technique are surprisingly accurate. The absolute error E_a , defined here as the proposed value of $G(x)$ (proposed formula) minus its reference value (presented in specialized tables) falls below 0.01 for all considered values of X . Therefore, the relative

error E_r is easily calculated by dividing the absolute error by the reference value.

II. THEORY

Generalized factorial functions must be able to receive and return non-integer values for non-integer inputs that are not yet defined. Below we show that a suitable polynomial expression for $F(x)$ hence $G(x)$ in the interval x element of $]0.2]$ can be found. This means that the problem of finding a closed form of non-integrative expression for $G(x)$ is solved.

The required closed form polynomial-approximate expression should retain the mathematical and physical properties of $G(x)$, namely the conditions i-iv defined below.

The process of finding a polynomial function that represent the numerical best fit is called the method of least squares and takes the form $f(x) = c_0 + c_1 x + c_2 x^2 \dots + c_n x^n$ where n is the degree of the polynomial and c,s is a set of coefficients.

The Gamma function is a generalization of the factorial function to non-integer numbers.

Therefore, this polynomial should represent the best fit to the numerical values of the Gamma function in the interval $0 < X < 2$. is subjected to the following conditions:

- minimum of Gamma occurs at $x = 1.4616321$ and the corresponding value of $G(x)$ is 0.8856032.
- $G(1) = G(2) = 1$.
- $G(x) = (x-1) !$
- The recurrence relation, $G(x) = (x-1) \cdot G(x-1)$

We propose a simple preliminary approach other than the classical method of least-squares. The proposed preliminary approach that satisfy the following conditions [4,5].

For this objective we divide the interval $0 < x < \infty$ into three consecutive parts a, b and c .

A. x element of $]0.1]$

Here, the proposed second-order polynomial expression for the Gamma function is $G(x) = F(x-1)$ where $F(x)$ is the factorial function $x!$. F is approximated by,

$$F(x) = (1 - 0.46163 * x + 0.46163 * x * x) \dots \dots (2)$$

x element of $[0,1]$.

B. x element of [1,2]

The Gamma function is approximated via the expression,

$$G(x)=\Gamma(x)+0.3333/X^{*}1.5 \dots\dots\dots (3)$$

Where $1/3 * 1/X$. \sqrt{x} is a correction factor.

Note that expressions (2) and (3) solve the difficulty of establishing an approximate polynomial expression for $F(x)$ and therefore $G(x)$ in the interval $0 < X < 2$.

C. x element of [2,infinity]

We can here use the expression (4) supplemented by the expression (2) for the remaining fraction,

$$G(x)=F(x-1) \dots\dots\dots (4)$$

Equations 2, 3 and 4 were implemented in a suitable algorithm which produced the required numerical results for $G(x)$ in the interval $0 < x < \infty$.

In order not to worry too much about the details of the theory let us go directly to numerical results.

III. NUMERICAL RESULTS

Numerical results are presented in Table I. It presents some examples of numerical results of the proposed technique (denoted by $G1(x)$) compared to those of the numerical tables (denoted by $G2(x)$) that are obtained by numerical integration of Eq. 1.

The absolute error E_a is defined here as $G1(x)$ minus $G2(x)$ where $G1(x)$ is the measured value calculated by the proposed technique and $G2(x)$ is the reference value of Gamma function found in specialized tables.

The relative error $E_r = [(G1(x) - G2(x)) / G1(x)]$ can be easily calculated.

X	G1(X)	G2(X)	Absolute
Proposed	Tables	Error technique	[1,2,3] $E_a = G1 - G2$
0	0.00	Infinite	--
1	0.05	30.8088	--
2	0.10	11.52668	--
3	0.15	6.7124	--
4	0.20	4.6891	--
5	0.25	3.6161 3.5798	0.0363
6	0.30	2.9652	--
7	0.35	2.5340	--
8	0.40	2.2304	--
9	0.45	2.0069	--
10	0.50	1.8373 1.7735	0.0638
11	0.55	1.7057	--
12	0.60	1.6024	--
13	0.65	1.5209	--
14	0.70	1.4571	--
15	0.75	1.4081	--
16	0.80	1.3719	--
17	0.85	1.3471	--
18	0.90	1.3328	--
19	0.95	1.3283	--
20	1.00	1.0000 1.0000	0.0000
21	1.05	0.9781 0.9735	0.0046
22	1.10	0.9585 0.9514	0.0041
23	1.15	0.9411	0.9330 0.0081
24	1.20	0.9261	0.9182 0.0089
25	1.25	0.9134	0.9085 0.0049
26	1.30	0.9031 0.8975	0.0056
27	1.35	0.8950 0.8912	0.0038
28	1.40	0.8892	0.8873 0.0016
29	1.45	0.8857	0.8857 0.0000
30	1.50	0.8846	0.8862 -0.0016
31	1.55	0.8857	0.8889 -0.0032
32	1.60	0.8892	0.8935 -0.0043
33	1.65	0.8950	0.9001 -0.0051
34	1.70	0.9031	0.9086 -0.0035
35	1.75	0.9134	0.9191 -0.0043
36	1.80	0.9261	0.9314 -0.0047

37	1.85	0.9411		0.9456	-0.0045
38	1.90	0.9585		0.9618	-0.0033
39	1.95	0.9781		0.9799	-0.0018
40	2.00	1.0000	1.0000		0.0000
41	2.05	1.0242			
42	2.10	1.0508			
43	2.15	1.0796			
44	2.20	1.1108			
45	2.25	1.1443			
46	2.30	1.1800			
47	2.35	1.2181			
48	2.40	1.2585			
49	2.45	1.3012			
50	2.50	1.3462	1.3293		0.0171
51	2.55	1.3935			
52	2.60	1.4432			
53	2.65	1.4951			
54	2.70	1.5493			
55	2.75	1.6059			
56	2.8	1.6647			
57	2.85	1.7259			
58	2.90	1.7894			
59	2.95	1.8552			
60	3.00	2.0000	2.0000		0.0000
61	3.05	2.1053			
62	3.10	2.2140			
63	3.15	2.3270			
64	3.20	2.4450			
65	3.25	2.5691			
66	3.3	2.7001			
67	3.35	2.8393			
68	3.40	2.9877			
69	3.45	3.1466			
70	3.50	3.3172	3.3234		-0.0062
71	3.55	3.5009			
72	3.60	3.6991			
73	3.65	3.91330			
74	3.70	4.1450			
75	3.75	4.3960			
76	3.8	4.6677			
77	3.85	4.9622			
78	3.90	5.2811			
79	3.95	5.6264			
80	4.00	6.0000	6.0000		0.0000
81	4.05	6.4212			
82	4.10	6.8635			
83	4.15	7.3300			
84	4.20	7.8240			
85	4.25	8.3495			
86	4.30	8.9105			
87	4.35	9.5117			
88	4.40	10.1583			
89	4.45	10.8558			
90	4.50	11.6101			

Table 1: Some examples of numerical results of the proposed technique compared to those of the numerical tables of ref.1,2,3

A portion of the numerical results of Table I is shown schematically in Figure 1 below.

Fig 1: Part of the Gamma function $G(x)$ vs x .

IV. CONCLUSION

We propose a semi-statistical technique to calculate the value of the Gamma function $G(x)$ in the whole space of positive x , i.e. $0 < x < \infty$.

The proposed method is simple and applies a second-degree polynomial fit to find accurate values for $\Gamma(x)$ in the interval $0 < x \leq 2$.

The precision of the numerical results of the new method is striking as shown in Table I where the absolute error is limited to less than 0.01 for the interval considered (x element of $]0, 5]$).

We recommend the application of the proposed technique for practical cases of calculation of the gamma function in order to avoid the complication of its numerical integration.

NB. All calculations in this article were produced using the author's double-precision algorithm to ensure maximum accuracy, as follows by ref. 6 for example

REFERENCES

- [1.] Wikipedia, Particular values of the gamma function.
- [2.] Apoorva Bali - Feb 22, 2023 Beta and Gamma Functions: Definition, Relationship, Properties & Applications.
- [3.] Wiley Online Library-Appendix B: Gamma Function Tables.
- [4.] I.M.Abbas, IJISRT Journal, Mars 2023.
- [5.] I.M.Abbas, Researchgate, Mars 2023.
- [6.] I.M.Abbas, IEEE, 1996, Pseudo-discharge spark. Plasma Science Transactions 24(3):1106 - 1119, DOI: 10.1109/27.533119.